

**BOUNDED MEAN OSCILLATION:
AN \mathbb{R} -FUNCTION WITH MULTI- \mathbb{K}_6 CUBES.
DUAL OF THE HARDY SPACE H^1 AND BANACH EXTENT**

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ABSTRACT. This paper investigates the concept of harmonic functions of bounded mean oscillation, starting from John–Nirenberg’s pioneering studies, under a renewed formalism, suitable for bringing out some fundamental properties inherent in it. In more detail: after a quick introduction, the second Section presents the main theorem, plus complete proof, relating to this function; in the third Section there is a suggestion on the exponential integrability (theorem and sketch of proof), while the fourth Section deals with the duality of Hardy space H^1 and bounded mean oscillation, with some ideas for a demonstration. The writing closes with a graphic appendix.

KEYWORDS: \mathbb{K}_6 cubes, Banach space, bounded mean oscillation, duality of Hardy space H^1 , exponential integrability, harmonic functions.

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1. A Few Words of Introduction

Bounded mean oscillation indicates an \mathbb{R} -function characterized by a finite mean oscillation. This can be expressed by a theorem, investigated by F. John and L. Nirenberg [7] in 1961. Let us try to give a more modern and concise form to this theorem, so as to outline some of its essential peculiarities in a few quick strokes. We will also take a look at the integrability of this harmonic function, and especially at its function space.

2. Bounded Mean Oscillation's Statement: How to do Harmonic Analysis with Cubes

Theorem 2.1. *Let $\varphi[\mathbb{R}]$ be a function of bounded mean oscillation, i.e. $\varphi \in \varphi_{\text{b}\sim}^{[\mathbb{R}]}$, $\mathbb{R} \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} \mathbb{R}^n$, for any cube \mathbb{K}_6 , and multi-index $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n) \in \mathbb{Z}_* = \{0\} \cup \mathbb{Z}_+$ of order $|\alpha| \leq k \in \mathbb{Z}_*$, where $\alpha > 0$ and $|\alpha| = \alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_n$. One has the inequality*

$$\left| \left(x \in \mathbb{K}_6 : \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6} \varphi \right| > \alpha \right) \right| \leq e |\mathbb{K}_6| \exp \left\{ - \frac{(2^n e)^{-1} \alpha}{\|\varphi\|_{\text{b}\sim}} \right\}, \quad (1)$$

in which $N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6}$ denotes the average value of φ over \mathbb{K}_6 , and $\|\varphi\|_{\text{b}\sim} \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} \|\varphi\|_{\text{BMO}}$ (BMO is, patently, for bounded mean oscillation).

Proof. We start from a cube $\hat{\mathbb{K}}_6$, and we choose this principle:

$$\frac{1}{|\hat{\mathbb{K}}_6|} \int_{\hat{\mathbb{K}}_6} \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6} \varphi \right| dx > \varepsilon, \quad (2)$$

with a constant $\varepsilon > 1$. But immediately we realize that the principle (2) does not apply to \mathbb{K}_6 , and in fact: $\frac{1}{|\mathbb{K}_6|} \int_{\mathbb{K}_6} \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6} \varphi \right| dx \leq \|\varphi\|_{\text{b}\sim} = 1 < \varepsilon$.

We remember that $|\mathbb{K}_6|$ is the volume of \mathbb{K}_6 , which translates into its Lebesgue measure, $|\mathbb{K}_6| \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} \lambda(\mathbb{K}_6)$; idem for $|\hat{\mathbb{K}}_6| \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} \lambda(\hat{\mathbb{K}}_6)$, or for any other cube $|\mathbb{K}_{(\cdot)}| \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} \lambda(\mathbb{K}_{(\cdot)})$, plainly.

The next step is to take a cube $\mathbb{K}_6^a \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} \mathbb{K}_6$, and divide it into 2^n equal subcubes, so as to see if the resulting subcubes, which we can call $\hat{\mathbb{K}}_{6,r}^a$, satisfy the principle (2). Such a process is repeated an infinite number of times, in order to gain a multiset of cubes $\left\{ \mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta \right\}_r$ whose features are:

$$\left| \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6^a} \varphi \right| \leq \varepsilon \text{ almost everywhere on } \mathbb{K}_6^a \setminus \bigcup_r \mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta, \quad (3a)$$

$$\left| N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta} \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6^a} \varphi \right| \leq 2^n \varepsilon, \quad (3b)$$

$$\varepsilon < \left| \mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta \right|^{-1} \int_{\mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta} \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6^a} \varphi \right| dx \leq 2^n \varepsilon, \quad (3c)$$

$$\sum_r \left| \mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta \right| \leq 1/\varepsilon \sum_r \int_{\mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta} \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6^a} \varphi \right| dx \leq 1/\varepsilon |\mathbb{K}_6^a|. \quad (3d)$$

Remember that the interior of each $\mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta$ is included in \mathbb{K}_6^a . The symbolic apparatus (3) allows to hybridize the principle (2) with this new principle:

$$\frac{1}{|\hat{\mathbb{K}}_6|} \int_{\hat{\mathbb{K}}_6} \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta} \varphi \right| dx > \varepsilon, \quad (4)$$

which however is not satisfied by $\mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta$. The process of decomposition into 2^n equal subcubes mentioned above must therefore be replicated for $\mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta$, with the aim that the subcubes obtained can satisfy the new principle, thereby generating a multiset of cubes $\left\{ \mathbb{K}_{6,s}^\gamma \right\}_s$, which are contained in $\mathbb{K}_{6,r}^\beta$. This new subdivision satisfies any feature in (3), when \mathbb{K}_6^a is replaced with \mathbb{K}_6^β , and \mathbb{K}_6^β with \mathbb{K}_6^γ .

So let us proceed with a further principle, which is identical to that in (4), except that the average changes, that is

$$N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\gamma}.$$

Consequently, we get a multiset of cubes $\{\mathbb{K}_{6_t}^\delta\}_t$, each of which is contained in $\mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\gamma$. Here is the up-to-date list of features, with the formation of two sets of cubes, this time denoted by $\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda$:

$$\left| \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^{\lambda-1}} \varphi \right| \leq \varepsilon \text{ almost everywhere on } \mathbb{K}_{6_r}^{\lambda-1} \setminus \bigcup_r \mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda, \quad (5a)$$

$$\left| N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda} \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^{\lambda-1}} \varphi \right| \leq 2^n \varepsilon, \quad (5b)$$

$$\varepsilon < \left| \mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda \right|^{-1} \int_{\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda} \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^{\lambda-1}} \varphi \right| dx \leq 2^n \varepsilon, \quad (5c)$$

$$\sum_r \left| \mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda \right| \leq 1/\varepsilon \sum_{\dot{r}} \left| \mathbb{K}_{6_{\dot{r}}}^{\lambda-1} \right|. \quad (5d)$$

To follow some things to know (the rest is easily verifiable).

(i) The interior of each $\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda$ is included in some $\mathbb{K}_{6_{\dot{r}}}^{\lambda-1}$.

(ii) The feature (5a) is demonstrable via Lebesgue differentiation theorem [8] [9]: all points in $\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^{\lambda-1} \setminus \bigcup_r \mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda$ are associated with a succession of cubes that can be shrunk up to any spatial punctuality, subsequently the averages over each cube is at most ε .

(iii) The feature (5d) is provable with this formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_r \left| \mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda \right| &< 1/\varepsilon \sum_r \int_{\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda} \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^{\lambda-1}} \varphi \right| dx = 1/\varepsilon \sum_{\dot{r}} \int_{\mathbb{K}_{6_{\dot{r}}}^\lambda} \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_{\dot{r}}}^{\lambda-1}} \varphi \right| dx \\ &\leq 1/\varepsilon \sum_{\dot{r}} \int_{\mathbb{K}_{6_{\dot{r}}}^{\lambda-1}} \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_{\dot{r}}}^{\lambda-1}} \varphi \right| dx \\ &\leq 1/\varepsilon \sum_{\dot{r}} \left| \mathbb{K}_{6_{\dot{r}}}^{\lambda-1} \right| \|\varphi\|_{b\sim} \\ &= 1/\varepsilon \sum_{\dot{r}} \left| \mathbb{K}_{6_{\dot{r}}}^{\lambda-1} \right|. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Accordingly, from (5d) one achieves $\sum_r \left| \mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\lambda \right| \leq \varepsilon^{-\lambda} \left| \mathbb{K}_6^a \right|$. We are now able to write these inequalities:

$$\left| N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\beta} \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_s}^a} \varphi \right| \leq 2^n \varepsilon, \quad (7a)$$

$$\left| \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\beta} \varphi \right| \leq \varepsilon \text{ almost everywhere on } \mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\beta \setminus \bigcup_s \mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\gamma, \quad (7b)$$

$$\text{ergo } \left| \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_s}^a} \varphi \right| \leq 2^n \varepsilon + \varepsilon \text{ almost everywhere on } \mathbb{K}_{6_r}^\beta \setminus \bigcup_s \mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\gamma, \quad (7c)$$

$$\text{and, from (3a), } \left| \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_s}^a} \varphi \right| \leq 2^n (2\varepsilon) \text{ almost everywhere on } \mathbb{K}_6^a \setminus \bigcup_s \mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\gamma. \quad (7d)$$

Then

$$\left| \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\gamma} \varphi \right| \leq \varepsilon \text{ almost everywhere on } \mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\gamma \setminus \bigcup_t \mathbb{K}_{6_t}^\delta, \quad (8a)$$

$$\text{ergo } \left| \varphi - \mathbb{K}_6^a \varphi \right| \leq 2^n (3\varepsilon) \text{ almost everywhere on } \mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\gamma \setminus \bigcup_t \mathbb{K}_{6_t}^\delta, \quad (8b)$$

once we have combined $\left| N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\gamma} \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\beta} \varphi \right| \leq 2^n \varepsilon$ and $\left| N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_s}^\beta} \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_{6_s}^a} \varphi \right| \leq 2^n \varepsilon$.

The inequality (7d) permits to extend the procedure also on $\mathbb{K}_6^\alpha \setminus \bigcup_t \mathbb{K}_{6t}^\delta$, from which we derive a further relation between different values:

$$\left| \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6^\alpha} \varphi \right| \leq 2^n (\lambda \varepsilon) \text{ almost everywhere on } \mathbb{K}_6^\alpha \setminus \bigcup_t \mathbb{K}_{6t}^\lambda. \quad (9)$$

The expression (9) gives us the opportunity to define this containment:

$$\left| \left(x \in \mathbb{K}_6 : \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6} \varphi \right| > 2^n (\lambda \varepsilon) \right) \right| \subset \bigcup_r \mathbb{K}_{6r}^\lambda. \quad (10)$$

The way to prove the theorematic inequality (1) is to go through the inequality

$$\sum_r |\mathbb{K}_{6r}^\lambda| \leq \varepsilon^{-\lambda} |\mathbb{K}_6^\alpha|, \quad (11)$$

previously encountered, and the one present in the relation (9). Letting first $2^n (\lambda \varepsilon) < \alpha \leq 2^n (\lambda + 1) \varepsilon$, for $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda \geq 0$, and defining then $-\lambda \leq 1 - \alpha / 2^n \varepsilon$, the final formula, once it is determined that $\varepsilon = e > 1$, is

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \left(x \in \mathbb{K}_6 : \left| \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6} \varphi \right| > \alpha \right) \right| &\leq \left| \left(x \in \mathbb{K}_6 : \left| \varphi - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6} \varphi \right| > 2^n (\lambda \varepsilon) \right) \right|, \\ &\leq \sum_r |\mathbb{K}_{6r}^\lambda| \leq 1 / \varepsilon^\lambda |\mathbb{K}_6^\alpha| \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$= |\mathbb{K}_6| \exp \{-\lambda \log \varepsilon\} \leq |\mathbb{K}_6| \varepsilon \exp \left\{ -\frac{\alpha \lambda \log \varepsilon}{2^n \varepsilon} \right\}, \quad (13)$$

as required. \square

3. Cubic Exponential Integrability

The Theorem 2.1 implies that, for any $\varphi \in \varphi_{b\sim}^{[\mathbb{R}]}$, there is an exponential integrability over all \mathbb{K}_6 , i.e.

$$\frac{1}{|\mathbb{K}_6|} \int_{\mathbb{K}_6} \exp \left\{ \frac{\zeta \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6} \varphi \right|}{\|\varphi\|_{b\sim}} \right\} dx \leq 1 - \frac{2^n e^2 \zeta}{2^n e \zeta - 1}, \quad (14)$$

for some $\zeta < \frac{1}{2^n e}$. Which is proved by the resulting combination,

$$\frac{1}{|\mathbb{K}_6|} \int_{\mathbb{K}_6} \exp \left\{ \frac{\zeta \left| \varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6} \varphi \right|}{\|\varphi\|_{b\sim}} \right\} dx \leq \int_0^\infty e^\alpha \exp \left\{ -\frac{(2^n e)^{-1} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\zeta} \|\varphi\|_{b\sim} \right)}{\|\varphi\|_{b\sim}} \right\} d\alpha = c_{(\zeta)}, \quad (15)$$

for $\zeta < (2^n e)^{-1}$, where $c_{(\zeta)}$ is a constant.

4. Function Space of $\varphi_{b\sim}^{[\mathbb{R}]}$

Now let us talk about space in relation to our harmonic function.

4.1. Dual of the Hardy Space $H^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and Banach Extent

(1) As F. John [6] pointed out, the space of a function of bounded mean oscillation is but a (Lebesgue) function space. C. Fefferman [2], and later E.M. Stein [3, I, IV], have shown that there is a duality between the Hardy space $H^{p=1}$ and all bounded mean oscillation functions—which gives a characterization of H^p in terms of boundary properties of harmonic functions.^a Put otherwise,

^a A Hardy (or Hardy–Freidrich) space $H^p(\mathbb{R}^n)$, $0 < p < \infty$, more correctly defined as a real Hardy space on \mathbb{R}^n , is a space of distributions on the real line, whose singularity increases as p decreases. One of its most significant forms is that of space of all tempered distributions:

$$\|\varphi\|_{H^p} = \left\| \left(\sum_{r \in \mathbb{Z}} |\Delta_r(\varphi)|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\|_{L^p} < \infty, \quad 0 < p \leq 1.$$

Cfr. G.H. Hardy [5] and F. Freidrich [4].

- (i) a bounded mean oscillation $\varphi_{b\sim}$ is the dual of the Hardy space $H^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$,
- (ii) a continuous linear functional, say, \mathcal{I}_L on $H^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$ is realizable in terms of a mapping:

$$\mathcal{I}_L[\eta_h] = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \varphi(x)\eta_h(x)dx, \quad (16)$$

where $\varphi \in \varphi_{b\sim}^{[\mathbb{R}]}$, and $\eta_h \in H^1$. From Eq. (16) it is inferred that, for each $\varphi \in \varphi_{b\sim}^{[\mathbb{R}]}$, the functional $\mathcal{I}_L[\eta_h]$ is bounded on H^1 via an inequality of this kind:

$$\left| \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \varphi(\eta_h)dx \right| \leq c \|\varphi\|_{b\sim} \|\eta_h\|_{H^1}, \quad (17)$$

setting η_h in the Hardy subspace $H^1_\tau \subset H^1$. And hence it is useful to write that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \varphi(\eta_h)dx = \sum_j \kappa_j \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \varphi(x)\tau_j(x)dx, \quad (18)$$

clarified the detail that $\eta_h = \sum \kappa_j \tau_j$, and that η_h is convergent in $L^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$. The demonstration of inequality (17), for a bounded φ and for any $\eta_h \in H^1$, is finally given by

$$\left| \int \varphi(x)\eta_h(x)dx \right| \leq \sum_j \left| \frac{\kappa_j}{|\mathbb{B}_j|} \right| \int_{\mathbb{B}_j} |\varphi(x) - \varphi_{\mathbb{B}_j}| dx \leq \sum |\kappa_j| \cdot \|\varphi\|_{b\sim}, \quad (19)$$

given a ball $\mathbb{B}_j \in \mathbb{R}^n$, once the non-equality $|\tau_j(x)| \leq |\mathbb{B}_j|^{-1}$ is designated.

(2) It is possible to translate everything described above into a simple assertion: $H^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$ can be considered as a replacement for $L^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$, whilst $\|\varphi\|_{b\sim}$ plays the same role with respect to the space $L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)$ of bounded functions on \mathbb{R}^n .

(3) A bounded mean oscillation function (supported in a cube \mathbb{K}_6 on \mathbb{R}^n) is locally L^p -integrable,

$$\|\varphi\|_{b\sim} = \sup_{\mathbb{K}_6} \left\{ \frac{1}{|\mathbb{K}_6|} \int_{\mathbb{K}_6} |\varphi(x) - N_{(a)}^{\mathbb{K}_6} \varphi| dx \right\} < \infty, \quad 1 < p < \infty. \quad (20)$$

Which means that $\|\varphi\|_{b\sim}$ is the Banach space [1] of every function $\varphi \in L^1_{loc}(\mathbb{R}^n)$.

Graphic Appendix. Cubic Inclusion of Matryoshka-type

When it comes to cubes contained within other cubes, the simplified graphic representation is something like this,

with a inclusion of Matryoshka-type: $\{\mathbb{K}_6, \{\mathbb{K}_6, \{\mathbb{K}_6, \{\mathbb{K}_6\}\}\}\}$, where any $\mathbb{K}_6 = \{\emptyset\}$.

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